

Manual de instalação de software

R, RStudio & RTools

1. Como instalar R (<https://posit.co/download/rstudio-desktop/#download>)

1.1 Clicar em *Download and Install R*.

The screenshot shows the RStudio Desktop download page. The page is titled "RStudio Desktop" and includes a navigation menu at the top with links for PRODUCTS, SOLUTIONS, LEARN & SUPPORT, EXPLORE MORE, and PRICING. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column is titled "1: Install R" and contains the text "RStudio requires R 3.6.0+. Choose a version of R that matches your computer's operating system." Below this text is a blue button labeled "DOWNLOAD AND INSTALL R", which is circled in red and has a red arrow pointing to it. The right column is titled "2: Install RStudio" and contains a blue button labeled "DOWNLOAD RSTUDIO DESKTOP FOR WINDOWS". Below this button, the page lists the size (263.07 MB), SHA-256 hash (A487AAC6), version (2024.04.0+735), and release date (2024-04-29). At the bottom of the page, there is a section titled "All Installers and Tarballs" which contains a table with columns for OS, Download, Size, and SHA-256. The table lists two operating systems: Windows 10/11 and macOS 12+.

OS	Download	Size	SHA-256
Windows 10/11	RSTUDIO-2024.04.0-735.EXE	263.07 MB	A487AAC6
macOS 12+	RSTUDIO-2024.04.0-735.DMG	565.12 MB	BE94CF88

1.2 Clicar na versão para o sistema operativo pretendido (Linux, macOS ou Windows).

The Comprehensive R Archive Network

Download and Install R

Precompiled binary distributions of the base system and contributed packages, **Windows and Mac** users most likely want one of these versions of R:

- [Download R for Linux \(Debian, Fedora/Redhat, Ubuntu\)](#)
- [Download R for macOS](#)
- [Download R for Windows](#)

R is part of many Linux distributions, you should check with your Linux package management system in addition to the link above.

Source Code for all Platforms

1.3 Exemplo para instalação em Windows: clicar em *install R for the first time*.

R for Windows

Subdirectories:

- [base](#): Binaries for base distribution. **This is what you want to *install R for the first time*.**
- [contrib](#): Binaries of contributed CRAN packages (for R >= 4.0.x).
- [old contrib](#): Binaries of contributed CRAN packages for outdated versions of R (for R < 4.0.x).
- [Rtools](#): Tools to build R and R packages. This is what you want to build your own packages on Windows, or to build R itself.

Please do not submit binaries to CRAN. Package developers might want to contact Uwe Ligges directly in case of questions / suggestions related to Windows binaries.

You may also want to read the [R FAQ](#) and [R for Windows FAQ](#).

Note: CRAN does some checks on these binaries for viruses, but cannot give guarantees. Use the normal precautions with downloaded executables.

1.4 Exemplo para instalação em Windows: clicar em *Download R-4.4.0 for Windows*.

R-4.4.0 for Windows

[Download R-4.4.0 for Windows \(82 megabytes, 64 bit\)](#)

[README on the Windows binary distribution](#)

[New features in this version](#)

This build requires UCRT, which is part of Windows since Windows 10 and Windows Server 2016. On older systems, UCRT has to be installed manually from [here](#).

If you want to double-check that the package you have downloaded matches the package distributed by CRAN, you can

2. Como instalar o RStudio (<https://posit.co/download/rstudio-desktop/#download>)

2.1 Clicar em *Download and Install R*.

The screenshot shows the RStudio Desktop download page. A red oval highlights the '2: Install RStudio' section, which includes a blue button labeled 'DOWNLOAD RSTUDIO DESKTOP FOR WINDOWS' with a red arrow pointing to it. Below the button, the file size (263.07 MB), SHA-256 hash (A487AAC6), version (2024.04.0+735), and release date (2024-04-29) are listed. A dark blue bar at the bottom of the page reads 'All Installers and Tarballs'. Below this, a note states 'RStudio requires a 64-bit operating system.' and another note mentions that Linux users may need to import Posit's public code-signing key. At the bottom, a table lists download links for Windows 10/11 and macOS 12+.

1: Install R

RStudio requires R 3.6.0+. Choose a version of R that matches your computer's operating system.

2: Install RStudio

DOWNLOAD RSTUDIO DESKTOP FOR WINDOWS

Size: 263.07 MB | SHA-256: A487AAC6 | Version: 2024.04.0+735 | Released: 2024-04-29

All Installers and Tarballs

RStudio requires a 64-bit operating system.

Linux users may need to import Posit's public code-signing key prior to installation, depending on the operating system's security policy.

OS	Download	Size	SHA-256
Windows 10/11	RSTUDIO-2024.04.0+735.EXE	263.07 MB	A487AAC6
macOS 12+	RSTUDIO-2024.04.0+735.DMG	565.12 MB	BE94CF08

3. Como instalar o RTools (<https://cran.r-project.org/bin/windows/Rtools/>)

3.1 Clicar na versão mais recente (compatível com a versão de R previamente instalada).

RTools: Toolchains for building R and R packages from source on Windows

Choose your version of Rtools:

RTools 4.4	for R versions from 4.4.0 (R-release and R-devel)
RTools 4.3	for R versions 4.3.x (R-oldrelease)
RTools 4.2	for R versions 4.2.x
RTools 4.0	for R from version 4.0.0 to 4.1.3
old versions of RTools	for R versions prior to 4.0.0

3.2 Clicar em *RTools44 installer* ou em *64-bit ARM Rtools44 installer*.

Rtools44 for Windows

Rtools is a toolchain bundle used for building R packages from source (those that need compilation of C/C++ or Fortran code) and for building R itself. Rtools44 is currently used for R 4.4 and R-devel, the development version of R, to become R 4.5.0.

Rtools44 consists of Msys2 build tools, GCC 13/MinGW-w64 compiler toolchain, libraries built using the toolchain, and QPDF. Rtools44 supports 64-bit Windows and UCRT as the C runtime.

Compared to Rtools43, Rtools44 for 64-bit Intel machines has newer versions of three core components: GCC, MinGW-w64, and binutils. It is therefore recommended to re-compile all code with the new toolchain to avoid problems. The code compiled by Rtools older than Rtools42 is incompatible due to use of MSVCRT and has to be recompiled with Rtools44 for use in R packages.

Rtools44 is also available for 64-bit ARM machines (aarch64): it includes Msys2 build tools (64-bit Intel builds running via emulation) and aarch64 builds of LLVM 17/MinGW-w64 compiler toolchain, libraries built using the toolchain, and again QPDF. The 64-bit ARM version of Rtools44 is experimental: a number of CRAN packages don't work with it and the Fortran compiler (flang-new) is not yet able to compile Fortran code of all CRAN packages. A number of CRAN packages doesn't work because they require not-yet-available 64-bit ARM versions of external software.

Installing Rtools44

Rtools is only needed for installation of R packages from source (those that need compilation of C/C++ or Fortran code) or building R from source. R can be installed from the R binary installer and by default will install binary versions of CRAN packages, which does not require Rtools44.

Moreover, online build services are available to check and build R packages for Windows, for which again one does not need to install Rtools44 locally. The [Winbuilder](#) check service uses identical setup as the CRAN incoming packages checks and has already all CRAN and Bioconductor packages pre-installed.

Rtools44 may be installed from the [Rtools44 installer](#) or [64-bit ARM Rtools44 installer](#). It is recommended to use the defaults, including the default installation location of C:\rtools44.

